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BioExcel-2 Project Number 823830

D6.1 – Management Plan

WP6: Management

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Executive Summary

This document describes BioExcel-2's management structure, the organization of different units, contact personnel and operational planning (including collaborative tools) for the duration of the entire project. The described procedures and practices may be changed in future as needs arise.

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1 Introduction

This document should be read in conjunction with the BioExcel-2 Grant Agreement, including the Description of Action and the Consortium Agreement. It contains information about partner contacts, email lists, project website, collaboration tools and reporting. Further procedures regarding the quality assurance processes, including documents rules, deliverables and approval procedures, and publications, and presentations will be defined in the upcoming deliverable D6.2 - *Quality Assurance and Risk Management Plan*.

We refer to BioExcel as the “project” in the context of the EU funded framework; as the “sustainable centre” regarding an organization past the BioExcel-2 funding scheme; and as the “centre” or “CoE” as the organizational structure existing both during and after the current grant consortium agreement.

2 Partner List

The BioExcel-2 Consortium includes 14 partners from 8 EU countries and 1 European country as listed in Table 1.

Beneficiary number	Beneficiary name	Beneficiary short name	Country
1	Kungliga Tekniska Högskolan	KTH	SE
2	Universiteit Utrecht	UU	NL
3	Fundacio Institut de Recerca Biomedica (IRB Barcelona)	IRB	ES
4	Forschungszentrum Julich	JUELICH	DE
5	The University of Edinburgh	UEDIN	UK
6	The University of Manchester	UMAN	UK
7	University of Jyväskylä	JYU	FI
8	European Molecular Biology Laboratory	EMBL	DE
9	Max Planck Gesellschaft zur Förderung der Wissenschaften e.V.	MPG	DE
10	AcrossLimits	AL	MT
11	BSC Barcelona – Centro Nacional de Supercomputacion	BSC	ES
12	Ian Harrow Consulting	IHC	UK
13	Norman Consulting	NC	NO
14	Nostrum Biodiscovery	NBD	ES

Table 1. Partner List

3 Contacts and Email lists

Contacts of the administrative personnel, partner representatives and work package leaders are presented in the following tables.

3.1 Contacts for Administrative, Legal and Financial Aspects

Partner	Name	Email
KTH	Anette Arling	an1@kth.se
UU	Ron Gunnewer Reinout Raijmakers	H.J.Gunneweg@uu.nl R.Raijmakers@uu.nl
IRB	Raquel Furio Natalia Marrugat Sònia Saborit	raquel.furio@irbbarcelona.org natalia.marrugat@irbbarcelona.org sonia.saborit@irbbarcelona.org
JUELICH	Jutta Stier	j.stier@fz-juelich.de
UEDIN	Andrew McDonald, Mark Parsons	a.mcdonald@epcc.ed.ac.uk , m.parsons@epcc.ed.ac.uk
UMAN	Shoaib Sufi	shoaib.sufi@manchester.ac.uk CompSciResearchfinance@manchester.ac.uk
JYU	Gerrit Groenhof Eeva Riipinen	gerrit.x.groenhof@jyu.fi eeva.riipinen@jyu.fi
EMBL	Rachel Curran	grants@ebi.ac.uk
MPG	Kerstin Mosch	eu-finance@rzg.mpg.de , eu-goe@gwdg.de
AL	Angele Giuliano	angele@acrosslimits.com
BSC	Ezequiel Mas Del Molino	ezequiel.masdelmolino@bsc.es
IHC	Ian Harrow	ianharrowconsulting@gmail.com
NC	Richard Norman	richard@normanconsulting.no
NBD	Robert Soliva	rsoliva@nostrumbiodiscovery.com

3.2 Contacts for Partner Representatives

Partner	Name	Email
KTH	Erwin Laure	erwinl@pdc.kth.se
UU	Alexandre Bonvin	a.m.j.bonvin@uu.nl
IRB	Modesto Orozco	modesto.orozco@irbbarcelona.org
JUELICH	Paolo Carloni	p.carloni@fz-juelich.de
UEDIN	Mark Parsons	m.parsons@epcc.ed.ac.uk
UMAN	Carole Goble	carole.goble@manchester.ac.uk
JYU	Gerrit Groenhof	gerrit.x.groenhof@jyu.fi
EMBL	Sarah Butcher	sarahb@ebi.ac.uk
MPG	Bert de Groot	bgroot@gwdg.de
AL	Angele Giuliano	angele@acrosslimits.com
BSC	Josep Lluís Gelpi	josep.gelpi@bsc.es
IHC	Ian Harrow	ianharrowconsulting@gmail.com
NC	Richard Norman	richard@normanconsulting.no

NBD	Robert Soliva	rsoliva@nostrumbiodiscovery.com
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3.3 Contacts for Work Package Leaders

Partner	Name	Email
WP1 leader	Mark Abraham (KTH)	mark.j.abraham@gmail.com
WP1 deputy	Brian Jimenez Garcia (UU)	b.jimenezgarcia@uu.nl
WP2 leader	Adam Hospital (IRB)	adam.hospital@irbbbarcelona.org
WP2 deputy	Stian Soiland-Reyes (UMAN)	soiland-reyes@manchester.ac.uk
WP3 leader	Arno Proeme (EPCC)	a.proeme@epcc.ed.ac.uk
WP3 deputy	Richard Norman (NC)	richard@normanconsulting.no
WP4 leader	Vera Matser (EMBL)	matser@ebi.ac.uk
WP4 deputy	Rossen Apostolov (KTH)	rossen@kth.se
WP5 leader	Angele Giuliano (AL)	angele@acrosslimits.com
WP5 deputy	Ian Harrow (IHC)	ianharrowconsulting@gmail.com
WP6 leader	Rossen Apostolov (KTH)	rossen@kth.se
WP6 deputy	Erwin Laure (KTH)	erwinl@pdc.kth.se

3.4 Email lists

Email communication within the consortium is facilitated by four main email distribution lists - *Bioexcel-all* includes all members of the project and is used for discussions concerning everyone involved; *Bioexcel-eb* is used by the Executive Board (EB) for coordination of the operations; *Bioexcel-pmb* for Project Management Board (PMB) communication; and *Bioexcel-finance* for financial topics. Additional mailing lists may be established on demand.

List Name	Purpose
bioexcel-all@pdc.kth.se	All members of the Project
bioexcel-pmb@pdc.kth.se	PMB Members
bioexcel-eb@pdc.kth.se	EB Members (WP leaders/deputies)
bioexcel-finance@pdc.kth.se	Financial contacts

4 Project Organization and Management

Here we describe the overall organization and management of the project. As one of the main goals of BioExcel is to establish a sustainable commercial arm of the center, this management structure is also responsible to enable the creation of the latter. Dedicated management structures and procedures for the emerging legal entity will be developed during the course of the project and presented in WP5 deliverables related to the business plan, namely D5.4 and D5.5.

4.1 Management structure

The management structure is designed to ensure the implementation of the overall project objectives in an efficient and secure way. The individuals selected for leading project positions hold similar positions in ongoing projects and have extensive experience from international collaborative projects, and in delivery of

high-quality research and development, support and training. Accurate quantitative and qualitative metrics for the project and its activities will be defined in the upcoming deliverable D6.2 - *Quality Assurance and Risk Management Plan*.

Due to the size of the consortium and the complexity of the project, a lean management structure has been chosen to ensure successful technical and administrative execution of the project. Central to the management of the project is a series of Boards and associated roles as described below.

4.2 Project Management Board

The ultimate authority of the project is the Project Management Board (PMB), composed of one member per partner. The PMB will meet every 6 months, by telephone or in person, with at least one meeting per year in person. More frequent meetings will be called if necessary to deal with extraordinary issues. The PMB will be chaired by the Centre Director (Erwin Laure, KTH).

The PMB is responsible for approving major changes in project plans, including changing partner budgets if required to realise project plans and objectives. The PMB will monitor the project status based on regular progress reports provided by the Centre Director and approve project deliverables and reports. The PMB may request revised project plans from the Centre Director should a status review or external events warrant such a request.

The intricacies of the consortium relations will be governed by a detailed Consortium Agreement, which has been drawn up with the assistance of the legal services of the coordinating partner in close collaboration with the participating institutes. This agreement also specifies clear conditions by which responsibility and corresponding EU funding will be re-assigned to other partners in case of persistent failure to meet delivery schedules. To ensure user representation, the chairs of the Scientific and Industrial Advisory Boards (Section 4.6) will be co-opted to the PMB as non-voting observers.

The main tasks of the PMB are to:

- Set the strategic direction of the project and its roadmap and technical vision;
- Ensure that the work of the project is focused towards achieving sustainability;
- Advise the Executive Board in the management of the project;
- Monitor on behalf of the partners the management of the project;
- Address external risks which may impair progress towards the Project's objectives and propose strategies to address those risks;
- Delegate responsibility for the day-to-day running of the project to the Centre Director with support from the Executive Board;
- Give guidance to the work of the project through the Centre Director;
- Address and document all issues raised by external regulatory and other bodies relevant to the objectives of the project;

- Ensure proper implementation of the rights and obligations of all Partners in accordance with the Contract and the Consortium Agreement;
- Approve any amendments to the Contract and Consortium Agreement;
- Address ethical, legal and gender issues relevant to the project;
- Decide upon the inclusion and exclusion of Partners;
- Approve project budgets;
- Assess performance of the project and take appropriate measures if performance is found to be lacking;
- Address all relevant Intellectual Property issues raised by Participants;
- Resolve any conflict between the Executive Board and any Partner.

4.3 Conflict resolution

An important role of the PMB is to arbitrate between partners should conflict arise. If the issue cannot be resolved within the project, an external arbitrator will be appointed, as described in the Consortium Agreement. The provision in the Consortium Agreement in this regard is a customary mediation plus arbitration clause (ref. section 11.8 of the DESCA Model Agreement). It is set out explicitly in the Consortium Agreement that, although one of the tasks of the Project Management Board is to arbitrate between the Parties, a Party may nonetheless opt to initiate mediation and arbitration in accordance with Section [11.8] of the Consortium Agreement at any time.

4.4 Executive Board

The executive management of the project will be coordinated by the Executive Board (EB), composed of the work package leaders and deputies (see section 3.3), the Scientific Director (Erik Lindahl, KTH), the Commercial Director (Angele Giuliano, AL), and chaired by the Executive Director (Rossen Apostolov, KTH). The EB will ensure the progress of the project with respect to the Description of Action (including reporting, deliverables and milestones monitoring, key event coordination, and relations with collaborating projects) and will meet every second week (teleconference or phone). Issues not resolved in the EB will be forwarded by the Executive Director to the PMB. The main tasks of the EB are to:

- Direct the project according to the work plan taking corrective actions as needed;
- Ensure deliverables are of good quality and on time;
- Support the Executive Director in all reporting activities towards the Project Board and EC;
- Ensure that there is a shared technical vision across all activities;
- Monitor progress towards the technical objectives of the project;
- Ensure that the technical activities interact effectively;
- Ensure the free flow of information between the activities;
- Prepare and update quality-assurance procedures and guidelines;
- Ensure that the interdependencies of the technical activities are effectively addressed;

- Identify and address technical risks, which may impair progress towards the Project's technical objectives and propose strategies to address these risks.

To improve information flow between the partners and the collaborative spirit of the project, all-hands meetings will be organized every 6 months to assess the progress made and provide detailed planning of the next steps. See section 5.1 for a list of various meetings.

The CoE will be led by the Executive Director supported by the relevant administrative, legal and financial support team in the management activity WP6, who will report directly to and liaise with the European Commission. The Executive Director reports to the PMB. The Executive Director will:

- Set up the overall management structure according to the management plan.
- Resolve issues with support from the Centre Director.
- Provide administrative support to partners via the Project Office support team.
- Chair the Executive Board (EB) and ensure effective management is implemented at all levels of the project organisation.
- Ensure effective operation of the project and ensure that all partners' efforts are focused towards achieving its objectives and deliverables.
- Act as primary point of contact between the project and the EC.
- Ensure timely delivery of project deliverables to the EU.
- Ensure documentation and dissemination of project results by responsible partners.
- Provide Periodic Activity Reports as requested by the EU.
- Provide Management Report as requested by the EU.
- Act as primary point of management contact with other related National and European projects and initiatives.
- Other responsibilities as defined by the Contract and the Consortium Agreement.

4.5 Work packages

The technical and scientific management structure draws on the work packages (WPs) with an overall management structure, particularly the EB, to ensure the coherence of the project. A dedicated Scientific Director will further ensure the scientific directions and coherence of the CoE and a dedicated Commercial Director will monitor the results of the project and assess their innovation and exploitation potential as described in Task 5.1. Each Work Package Leader is responsible for providing the Executive Director with detailed plans for the activities, and for the implementation of plans approved by the Executive Director. Work Package Leaders may request change of plans or staffing as warranted by project outcomes or insights gained. Work Package Leaders report to the Executive Director. This management structure permits on-going monitoring of the progress of the project against the work plan, with effective problem detection

and resolution processes in place. All work package leaders and deputy leaders have been nominated by the Executive Director and approved by the Project Management Board. Each Work Package Leader is responsible for:

- Coordinating the communication and work between partners within their work package;
- Understanding work package constraints and coordination issues;
- Ensuring progress towards work package milestones and deliverables;
- Ensure that all work package reports and deliverables are produced in a timely fashion;
- Ensure that results and outputs are disseminated effectively to other work packages and in particular the Dissemination Work Package Leader;
- Ensure good communication with other work packages;
- Reporting the progress of their work package to the Executive Board;
- Providing support for the Executive Director via the Executive Board.

Work package leaders will be expected to set up regular meetings between participants within their work package.

Deputy work package leaders will maintain an awareness of the work package leader responsibility outcomes and will step in for the work package leader if required.

4.6 Scientific Advisory Board and Industrial Advisory Board

The project will have a Scientific Advisory Board (SAB) and an Industrial Advisory Board (IAB), which will provide objective external feedback on the strategic direction of the BioExcel-2 project. The SAB will initially consist of 4-5 academic members with an appropriate background. We will consider both existing SAB members active in the previous project, provided their continued availability as well as new members. Likewise, the IAB will be composed of 4-5 industry representatives, from companies from pharmaceutical, chemical and food industry sectors, software vendors and technology developing SMEs. The members of the SAB and IAB will be confirmed in the first months of the project (milestone M7) and additional members will be added during the project from the BioExcel-2 user base. The chairs of the SAB and IAB will be co-opted to the PMB.

The overall management structure is schematically represented in Figure 1 below.

Figure 1. Project Management Structure

5 Operational management processes

5.1 Project meeting schedule

Meetings will be held according to the following schedule:

- EB – the main activity for project execution and coordination is run as video teleconference meetings once every two weeks
- PMB – face-to-face meetings twice a year, typically during the project all-hands meetings
- WP – organized as needed by the WP leaders, typically also once every two weeks virtually but also in person if there is a need for better / faster work co-ordination
- All-hands meetings – twice a year all project partners meet for typically a two-day event

5.2 Decision making

As mentioned above, center operations are run by the EB, which is responsible for making decisions regarding ongoing work. Those are discussed during the regular teleconference meetings and WP specific tasks are agreed during separate teleconference (or face-to-face) meetings of personnel involved. All decisions are shared with the PMB.

Higher-level and strategic decisions are raised to the PMB for approval.

Each WP leader is responsible to ensure that the necessary progress is made along planned WP activities. All WP leaders oversee the work and communicate directly with all the personnel (from different partners) who are part of that WP. Thus, day-to-day decisions are taken by WP members and their outcome is reported to the EB during regular teleconferences.

5.3 Conflict resolution

If conflict arises within a WPs' activities, this is first discussed at an EB meeting. If the conflict cannot be resolved by the EB, it is escalated to the PMB. If the conflict cannot be resolved by the PMB, an external arbitrator is appointed, as described above in section 4 with reference to the Consortium Agreement section 11.8.

5.4 Quality control

Work package leaders oversee the tasks and activities in the respective packages and progress is reported to the EB. Results are discussed at the regular teleconferences and face-to-face meetings. Progress against KPIs and monitoring of risks are monitored quarterly.

All documents such as deliverables, reports, press releases as well as printed material (flyers, posters, roll-up etc.) are reviewed for acceptance by the PMB. Web content is curated by a designated member from the outreach team. Support forums are monitored by a number of administrators and members of the user support team.

More details on quality control processes and procedures will be presented in D6.2 "Quality assurance and Risk Management"

5.5 Risk management

A number of potential risks and means for their mitigation are described in detail in D6.2 "Quality Assurance and Risk Management". The risks cover the important aspects of work in each of the WPs. Each risk has a person responsible for its monitoring and reporting to the EB. As a rule, risk assessment is done twice a year.

5.6 Rules and procedures

Members of the consortium are requested to follow a number of operational rules and expectations as agreed at the beginning of the project.

Operations

- Each partner organization has a representative in the PMB and they are expected to attend the PMB meetings. Minutes from the meetings are distributed to all partners as a notification of the decisions taken.
- Each partner appoints a designated person to lead the WP for which it is responsible. All WP leaders and their deputies are expected to attend all EB meetings.
- WP leaders are responsible for ensuring timely and quality execution of tasks within their WP. They are also responsible for curating the production of the respective deliverables, e.g. collecting contributions from partners and producing draft documents.

- All deliverables and associated reports are first reviewed by the EB. After that they are sent for approval to PMB. Documents are deposited in the EC portal and submitted to the commission by the Center Director (functioning as Project Coordinator in the grant agreement)(Sec. 4.2).

Documents management

- All documents relevant to the project work should be stored in the shared platform (see section 6.1)
- Deliverables and reports should use the document template as described in D4.1 “Dissemination and Outreach Plan”
- Presentation slides should be made using the presentation template as described in D4.1. If BioExcel-2 activities are included as part of a wider scope presentation, where the fully branded template is not suitable, then BioExcel’s logo should be used in the acknowledgement sections.
- Center logo and EU flag/project number should be present on all promotional material such as posters and flyers.
- Publications by the partners should include in the acknowledgements sections a standardized paragraph describing the funding of the project.
- It is encouraged that all publications should be submitted to journal adhering to the Open Access policy and registered with OpenAire repositories.
- Documents containing restricted intellectual property information may be subject to restricted access and may be shared via suitable agreements.

Web content management

- Every section of the website has a curator responsible (Michelle Mendonca) for gathering content for contribution from the partners. Before addition, the content is moderated by the curator who ensures the quality and sufficiency of the material.
- All partners are expected to notify the curator of news and information that is of interest for the community such as upcoming events, recent publications, recent software releases, notable achievements in the area. Reminders are being sent once a month.
- The curator also manages the center’s social outreach platforms such as Twitter channel, LinkedIn company page, YouTube channel.

Webinars

- The webinar educational series are produced live and recordings are made available on the center’s video channel. For that reason, we have three people who are responsible for smooth operation of the series with a requirement that each event is managed by two organizers for support. Organizers follow an extensive checklist for procedures before, during and after the completion of each webinar.

6 Project Management Tools

6.1 Document repositories

All documents needed or produced by the project are stored on a shared Google Drive platform. The platform is accessible by all consortium members.

Collaborative editing of documents is also using the Google Drive suite of applications. Google documents are also used for production of online surveys.

6.2 Task management

Keeping track of ongoing work is done using ClickUp (<https://clickup.com>). ClickUp is a web, mobile and desktop application which allows distributed teams to organize their tasks through an intuitive interface. It gives a good overview to WP leaders about ongoing work, upcoming deadlines etc.

Each task has an assigned person who is responsible for its completion by a specified date, but it might involve several members in certain cases.

In order to strengthen the joint activities across the team and avoid “work package silos”, projects and tasks in ClickUp are organized by process or activity. These are Code Development; Support and Training; Outreach and Events; Sustainability Management. They will be pulling in activities of different work packages.

The WP leaders and deputies are responsible for monitoring the progress with tasks, while other members can record progress with status, create new tasks with suggestions, ideas etc.

During EB meetings every WP leader (or deputy in his absence) reviews the progress in the different activities and tasks.

6.3 Code repositories

Improvements and contributions to existing tools and projects, part of BioExcel-2, will go back into their existing source code repositories, if such are already in use. Otherwise, newly developed open source code will be hosted on the GitHub platform (<https://github.com/bioexcel>) under the GitHub organization. This will be a “holding station” for contributions that should be contributed upstream, but are not yet in such a state. Details of the software process adopted by BioExcel-2 are described in D1.1 “Updated specification of development process”.

7 Conclusions

We have outlined the management structures of BioExcel. As activities and services of the center develop in the course of the EU project funding, additional dedicated managerial and operational structures might be set up to provide persistency and sustainability. This is a live document that will be kept updated throughout the lifetime of the project according to the needs arising.